

PRIORITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY IN TOURISM

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Abstract: The article explores the issues of improving the mechanisms for the development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism in our country. In the course of the study, a multi-factor analysis was carried out on the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector, taking it as an endogenous factor, influenced by its main factor (resources), and forecast indicators were developed by 2026. At the same time, an organizational and economic mechanism based on a cluster approach was proposed to effectively organize the activities of existing tourist enterprises in the regions of our country, and the ways of use in practice were based.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, tourism, tourist activity, tourist services market, gross value added, investment, tourist cluster, organizational and economic mechanism.

Introduction

The processes of globalization and economic integration in the world are gaining momentum, providing the basis for flexibility in the way of Human Life, expansion of inter-country labor migration, increased demand for the tourism sector and its Sustainable Development.

In the world, scientific research is carried out to develop all directions of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism, increase its change in the volume of gross domestic product and per capita services, provide the population with new jobs in the regions, and improve the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of entrepreneurial activity at enterprises of the industry. In this regard, the priority areas are to expand new structures of entrepreneurial activity in tourist enterprises, evaluate the competitiveness of entrepreneurial activity in tourist enterprises on the basis of improving models and mechanisms, as well as carry out scientific research on the use of investment mechanisms in supporting entrepreneurial activity in the field.

The role of the tourism sector in the development of the national economy is determined not only by its high income, but also by its positive impact on solving the employment problem by creating working industrial jobs, playing a key role in ensuring sustainable development through the preservation of the natural and cultural environment, significantly contributing to ensuring harmony between peoples and nations, and

The development of the tourism sector in the conditions of the implementation of structural changes in the direction of the comprehensive development of tourism activities in our country is expressed in the strategic goals and objectives established to ensure the development of the industry in 2022-2026. The successful implementation of these tasks requires the effective use of existing tourist resource components in the development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of Tourism of our country, the assessment of the effectiveness of entrepreneurial activity affecting the development of the territorial economy,

the use of competitive advantages in the activities of enterprises of the industry, the improvement of mechanisms related to the assessment

Thematic literature analysis

According to researchers who are conducting research on the development of field activities, the tourism industry is after the pandemic again predicts that the Re-economy will become a dynamic direction it is being done, from this point of view related areas, that is, transport (air traffic, rail, yerusti transport, water transport, transport development of tools), communications and logistics (communication tools, ICT, international relations, legal provision of the development of the economy, small and Organization of medium-sized business entities), infrastructure (hotels construction, national dining facilities and relaxation programs performed glazing), service areas (theater, music, historical and cultural sites, dining facilities and hotel business), new the high level of industries such as the labor market, the creation of jobs can serve as an impetus for the development of the level[1].

Tourism is derived from the French word *tour*, meaning hiking. In the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on tourism", the concept of tourism is defined as: "tourism – the departure (travel) of an individual for a period of one year, not engaged in paid activities in a place of recovery, educational, professional-practical or other purposes (in the country) from the place of permanent residence"¹.

Tourism is the ability of people to travel in their free time from their permanent residence in another country or within their own country for the purposes of impression and recreation, health restoration, hospitality, acquisition of knowledge or professional practical purposes, but not to engage in work motivated by money where they go [2].

S.A.Bistrov and M.G.Voronsova, on the other hand, writes that "the tourist services market is a general economic phenomenon that unites demand and supply to ensure the trading processes of specific tourist goods and services at a certain time and a certain place" [3]. YE.N.Ilina, on the other hand, the tourist market is mainly manifested in the system of economic interaction of the four main elements, namely, tourist demand, tourist product supply, price and competition. The modern tourist market is developed at a significant level, and, like other markets, it develops from the seller's market (in which the manufacturer decides what quantity and where to sell the product) to the buyer's market. The buyer determines what product, how much volume and at what price the manufacturer produces the product[4] - indicates.

Today, while the period of recovery in the tourism services market for the period before the pandemic on a global scale continues, countries are developing measures based on territorial approaches to the development of industry activities. In particular, in order to further develop the activities of the industry in our country, measures and meiori-documents of various manifestations are being developed at the government level. In order to compensate for the problems observed in entry and exit tourism during the pandemic, the maximum use of domestic tourism potential has also been made in our country. In this regard, the development of entrepreneurial activity in the tourism services market again and the support of the state on the basis of various benefits has become the same.

Analysis and results

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on tourism". Tashkent City, July 18, 2019, Orq-No. 549.

Without foreseeing the future, without forecasting the ways of its development, it is impossible to achieve the progress of the life of society. In recent years, forecasting economic processes has become one of the main tools for ensuring the optimal functioning of sectors and sectors of the economy. In the process of developing alternative scenarios for planning and development of the future period, forecasting acts as a means of anticipating the paths of socio-economic development in the scientific justification of society's production and its goals. Economic modeling in a market economy is necessary in order to be able to see how long and medium-term economically efficient directions, policies and decisions made are in practice. Production planning and management it is necessary to ensure the selection of optimal decisions and their implementation, since today the level of damage to society from unsubstantiated decision-making is growing many times. Therefore, modern business forecasting requires the expansion of the scope of its methods and methodologies to be improved[5].

A multi-factor analysis was carried out on the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector, taking it as an endogenous factor, influenced by its main factor (resource). Having determined the volume of income from the tourism sector as a high peak of the function, that is, as a result factor, the following indicators were selected based on an expert analysis of the indicators of the influencing factor with the participation of the leading experts of the Ministry of Tourism and cultural heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Table 1):

- X_1 – Gross Value Added created in tourism;
- X_2 – Number of tourists entering Uzbekistan;
- X_3 – the volume of investments in the tourism sector;
- X_4 – number of business entities in the field of Tourism;
- X_5 – the volume of real total income per capita.

When the essence of the indicators of the endogenous factor and the exogenous factor acting on it is seen, the influencing factors will have a connection close to the model in the form of a production model based on factor indicators that represent factors that have a significant impact through the volume of capital, resource and real total per capita income. Based on the linkage of the main endogenous and exogenous factors extracted, data in the form of the above time series was analyzed using the EViews10 program in order to determine the trends in the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector.

1- table

Indicators of the volume of income from the tourism sector and the factor affecting its change²

Years	Tourism	Gross	To	Tourism	Number	of	The
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² Developed by the author on the basis of data from the statistical agency under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

	scope removable revenue volume, billion. Soum (Y)	Value Added, created in the tourism sector, amounted to Rs. Soum (X ₁)	Uzbekistan penetration coming number of tourists, thousand people (X ₂)	scope entering volume of investments, mlrd. Soum (X ₃)	business entities in the field of Tourism, pcs (X ₄)	volume of real total income per capita, Rs. (X ₅)
2011	341,6	3294,7	1394,0	13,8	332,0	2729,9
2012	567,9	3561,5	1595,0	21,0	358,0	3267,8
2013	1112,3	3793,4	1698,0	15,9	336,0	3902,7
2014	1052,0	4066,4	1862,0	18,7	343,0	4472,0
2015	1187,5	4219,5	1917,0	18,5	398,0	5127,5
2016	1252,5	4253,3	2070,0	35,2	433,0	5887,9
2017	1546,9	4631,8	2691,0	31,7	499,0	6681,4
2018	1041,1	5085,7	5346,0	44,9	983,0	7767,0
2019	1313,0	6169,0	6748,0	87,5	1158,0	9509,6
2020	255,8	1240,0	1504,0	101,7	1337,0	10737,3
2021	422,1	1680,2	1685,0	580,2	1483,0	13325,8
2022	803,3	4186,1	3900,0	275,5	1433,7	12554,7

Using the identified data, a multi-factor econometric model of the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector and the influence of factors affecting it was compiled. According to it represents this process

$$\ln Y = 0,333 \cdot \ln X_1 + 0,695 \cdot \ln X_2 - 0,101 \cdot \ln X_3 - 1,742 \cdot \ln X_4 + 1,793 \cdot \ln X_5 - 5,548 \quad (1)$$

the regression equation is constructed.

When a defined linear logarithmic model is potentiated, an econometric model with a non-linear pattern follows, representing the volume of income from the tourism sector:

$$Y_1 = \frac{X_1^{0,333} \cdot X_2^{0,695} \cdot X_5^{1,793}}{X_3^{0,101} \cdot X_4^{1,742} \cdot e^{5,548}} \quad (2)$$

Using the multifactorial econometric model, the appearance in the graph of the values of the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector in the medium term, that is, in 2011-2026 (Figure 1) was expressed.

On the basis of the links of the above factor, a development scenario was developed by US based on the influence of factors on the volume of income from the tourism sector, which is considered the resulting indicator of the indicators that are considered the most important in the development of the tourism sector. The use of identified trends makes it possible to optimize the effect obtained from the unit of the resource with the correct distribution of the volume of the resource being introduced into the industry.

Figure 1. Change in the indicator of the volume of income from the tourism sector in 2011-2026³, crore (2022-2026 forecast)

Trend models determined on the basis of multifactorial linkage make it possible to predict in advance the change of the main indicators of field activity in the coming period, taking into account errors at a certain limit under the influence of selected factors. The change in the volume of income from the tourism sector in the research process is also used to determine the forecast values for the coming period, influenced by 5 main factors.

Above, it was recommended for use with systematization and improvement of the organizational and economic mechanism of the activities of tourism clusters, which ensures the effective development of the development of the industry, taking into account the models being developed in order to develop the tourism sector (Figure 2).

The proposed mechanism proposes measures to stimulate entrepreneurial activity in tourist enterprises for the normal functioning of cluster systems. In particular, to stimulate the initiative for the formation of a cluster, to form a regional tourism administration for the formation of a modern tourism cluster, to develop a strategy for promoting the cluster structure and the production of tourist products, to ensure the continuous and effective implementation of the preparatory process, etc.

³ Developed on the basis of author's research.

Figure 2. Organizational and economic mechanism of activity of tourism clusters⁴

The strengthening of the existing technological and scientific infrastructure serves as the basis for deepening the Integrative ties between research institutions and tourist enterprises. At the same time, it can significantly speed up the process of clustering tourist enterprises by increasing the interaction and dependence of socio-economic institutions. A high level of cluster efficiency is achieved with the effective functioning of organizational and economic mechanisms that stimulate the development of its subjects. In this case, the analysis of personnel of tourist enterprises shows the high age of employees and the separation of professional education in higher educational institutions from the production process. The solution to this problem is closely related to the development of a system for the targeted training of highly qualified specialists by replenishing standard educational programs with special programs aimed at the needs of specific tourist enterprises in the organization of the production of competitive tourist products using new innovative technologies.

The introduction of improved organizational and economic mechanisms in the research process in entrepreneurial activities of tourist enterprises, firstly, leads to an improvement in the conditions using state participation in the organization of activities, and secondly, it makes it possible to achieve a multiplicative effect by combining basic and additional activities on the path of a common goal.

Conclusions and suggestions

⁴ Developed by the author.

Based on the above tasks and practical results, the following suggestions and recommendations were made:

- the role of the tourism sector in the development of the national economy is determined not only by its high income, but also by its positive impact on the solution of the employment problem by creating working industrial jobs, playing a key role in ensuring sustainable development through the preservation of the natural and cultural environment, significantly contributing to ensuring harmony between peoples and;
- in the process of research, the impact of organizational and economic methods for the development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism on the development of the resource potential of the industry was determined. Entrepreneurial structures affect costs and profitability through effective economic systems, as a result, the overall efficiency of activities;
- a multi-factor analysis has been carried out on the change in the volume of income from the tourism sector under the influence of its main factor (resource), taking it as an endogenous factor. Having determined the volume of income from the tourism sector as a high peak of the function, that is, as a result factor, the indicators of the influencing factor were created on the basis of an expert analysis conducted with the participation of leading experts of the Ministry of Tourism and culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of gross value added, number of tourists entering, indicators such as the number of business entities in the tourism sector and the volume of real total income per capita were determined.
- an organizational and economic mechanism based on a cluster approach is proposed to effectively organize the activities of existing tourist enterprises in the regions of our country. In the tourist cluster, depending on the existing conditions, tourist enterprises offering tourist services as the main structure of the cluster are considered, while the elements in connection with the cluster are considered the administration of the territory, enterprises offering side and additional services within the cluster, and the area or region in which the cluster is developing. The mechanism of activity of tourism clusters, which takes into account internal and external relations, was to some extent formed and recommended for use in the research process, systematizing and improving this mechanism. The proposed mechanism proposes measures to stimulate entrepreneurial activity in tourist enterprises for the normal functioning of cluster systems.

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